

Impact of clinical pharmacy interventions on antibiotic prescribing appropriateness and associated factors in acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Thang Nguyen¹, Suol Thanh Pham¹, Phuong Minh Nguyen², Dyah Aryani Perwitasari³, Tho Kieu Anh Pham²

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacy, Can Tho University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Can Tho City, Vietnam

² Faculty of Medicine, Can Tho University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Can Tho City, Vietnam

³ Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Tho Kieu Anh Pham (pkatho@ctump.edu.vn)

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Abstract

Inappropriate antibiotic use during chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) exacerbations (AECOPD) drives antimicrobial resistance and preventable harm. Prescribing appropriateness was evaluated, associated factors were identified, with a prespecified focus on renal impairment, and a pharmacist-led intervention was assessed. In this two-phase study, 448 inpatient records (224 pre-intervention and 224 post-intervention) were reviewed before and after education, renal-dose support, and antibiotic-related drug–drug interaction consultation. Overall appropriateness increased from 40.6% to 65.6% after the intervention ($p = 0.018$), mainly through improvements in dose, dosing frequency, and avoidance of clinically relevant antibiotic-related interactions. Severe exacerbation, creatinine clearance ≤ 50 mL/min, and combination therapy independently predicted inappropriate prescribing. Pharmacist-led antimicrobial stewardship can substantially improve the quality of antibiotic prescribing in resource-limited hospitals.

Keywords

antimicrobial stewardship, creatinine clearance, dose adjustment, drug–drug interaction, Vietnam

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a long-term respiratory disorder characterized by progressive and largely irreversible airflow limitation. The condition primarily arises from chronic inflammation triggered by inhalation of harmful gases and particles, predominantly affecting the small airways and pulmonary parenchyma (Global Initiative for Chronic Ob-

structive Lung Disease 2024b). Acute exacerbations (AECOPD) are defined as sudden episodes of symptom worsening beyond normal day-to-day variation, typically presenting with increased breathlessness, greater sputum volume, and heightened sputum purulence (Wedzicha and Seemungal 2007). These events substantially accelerate disease progression, increase health care utilization, and elevate mortality risk (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2024b).

Bacterial infection plays a major role in the pathogenesis of AECOPD, accounting for approximately 50% of episodes (Sethi and Murphy 2008). Appropriate antibiotic therapy in confirmed bacterial exacerbations has been shown to reduce mortality by approximately 77%, decrease treatment failure by 53%, and lessen sputum purulence by 44% (Vollenweider et al. 2012). In contrast, inappropriate antibiotic prescribing—particularly empirical use without clear evidence of bacterial infection—can delay recovery, increase hospital readmissions, worsen lung-function decline, and negatively affect quality of life, emphasizing the need for strict adherence to evidence-based guidelines (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2024b).

Despite clear antibiotic prescribing recommendations provided by the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD), inappropriate antibiotic use remains common, contributing to the growing global burden of antimicrobial resistance (Mulchandani et al. 2025). Clinical pharmacy interventions have demonstrated effectiveness in addressing this issue. Pharmacist-led activities, including comprehensive medication reviews, individualized antibiotic dose optimization, and participation in multidisciplinary care teams, have significantly improved prescribing appropriateness and reduced unnecessary antibiotic use (Marins et al. 2024). Integrating clinical pharmacists into COPD management, therefore, holds considerable potential to promote rational antibiotic therapy and enhance clinical outcomes.

In Vietnam, clinical pharmacy efforts in the management of acute COPD exacerbations have traditionally focused on improving medication adherence and overall prescription rationality. However, limited attention has been directed toward patients with impaired renal function—a population at particularly high risk of adverse drug reactions and dosing errors (Luong et al. 2022). Previous studies consistently highlight gaps in antibiotic dose adjustment according to renal function, especially among older adults (Nguyen et al. 2021; Luong et al. 2022). Moreover, the clinical consequences of prescribing errors related to reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR) remain insufficiently explored.

These gaps underscore the need for targeted antimicrobial stewardship in AECOPD, particularly for patients with impaired renal function who are at high risk of dosing errors and adverse events. Accordingly, this study evaluated the appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing in hospitalized patients with AECOPD, identified factors associated with inappropriate prescribing, including renal impairment, and assessed the effectiveness of pharmacist-led interventions to improve prescribing quality.

Materials and methods

Study design and setting

A prospective, two-phase (pre-intervention and post-intervention) observational study with an embedded single-arm educational intervention was conducted. The study was conducted at the Respiratory Department of

[Provincial General Hospital name] in southern Vietnam. The pre-intervention data collection covered 1 October 2022–31 March 2023, and the post-intervention period covered 1 October 2023–31 March 2024. The intervention was implemented from July to September 2023.

Study population and eligibility

Two distinct participant groups were included: (1) medical records of inpatients diagnosed with AECOPD and (2) physicians prescribing antibiotics for these patients. Data were collected in two phases: pre-intervention (October 2022 to March 2023) and post-intervention (October 2023 to March 2024).

Inclusion criteria:

- Medical records of hospitalized patients diagnosed with AECOPD who received antibiotics during hospitalization.
- Physicians who prescribed antibiotics for these patients.

Exclusion criteria:

- Medical records of patients who received antibiotics for <72 h, were moved to another health care facility, left against physician advice, or had incomplete or inaccessible records.
- Physicians who did not continuously participate in patient management throughout the entire study period.

Sample size and sampling procedure

The sample size for the cross-sectional component was calculated using the formula $n = Z^2 \times p(1 - p) / d^2$ for a proportion, with $Z = 1.96$ (95% CI), $p = 0.7025$ (expected irrational antibiotic rate from prior local data; Ngo 2021), and margin of error $d = 0.06$, yielding $n = 224$ records per phase.

Medical records were selected by systematic random sampling each month. For each month, a random start (x) was generated using a table of random numbers, and every k th record was selected until 38 records per month were obtained ($k = \text{total monthly eligible records} / 38$). If a selected record met the exclusion criteria, it was replaced by the next eligible record on the list.

Data collection and variables

- **Patient variables:** age, sex, smoking status, exacerbation severity (clinically defined per GOLD/local criteria), comorbidities (number and types), hospital length of stay (days), antibiotic regimen type (monotherapy or combination), and renal function.
- **Renal function:** creatinine clearance (CrCl) was estimated using the Cockcroft–Gault equation with the patient's actual body weight recorded on admission or the most recent documented weight if admission weight

was unavailable. Serum creatinine was measured in the hospital laboratory using an enzymatic method traceable to isotope-dilution mass spectrometry (IDMS) and converted to mg/dL as needed. $\text{CrCl (mL/min)} = [(140 - \text{age}) \times \text{weight (kg)}] / [72 \times \text{serum creatinine (mg/dL)}] \times 0.85$ (if female). Patients were categorized as $\text{CrCl} > 50 \text{ mL/min}$ or $\leq 50 \text{ mL/min}$ for analysis.

- Antibiotic use variables included antibiotic class, initial regimen, regimen changes and their documented rationale, and duration of therapy. To reflect clinically relevant safety issues in routine care, key concomitant medications were also extracted. Prespecified clinically significant antibiotic-related drug–drug interactions were assessed using the Ministry of Health contraindicated interaction list (Decision No. 5948/QĐ-BYT) and two interaction databases (Drugs.com and Micromedex). The assessed interaction categories were fluoroquinolones co-prescribed with systemic corticosteroids, domperidone, metformin, theophylline/aminophylline, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and antacids or other cation-containing products (e.g., calcium, magnesium, aluminum, iron, or zinc preparations). The interaction assessment was limited to these pre-specified antibiotic-related combinations.

Antibiotic prescribing appropriateness was assessed against the hospital antibiotic protocol in effect during each phase, the corresponding national COPD guidance available at that time (2018 guidance during the pre-intervention phase and the updated 2023 guidance during the post-intervention phase), and the Vietnam National Formulary for dose recommendations. This approach was chosen to benchmark prescribing against the contemporaneous standard of care and to reflect real-world stewardship implementation following the guideline update.

- **Physician variables:** age (<40 or ≥ 40 years), gender, education level (undergraduate or postgraduate), and clinical experience (<5 or ≥ 5 years).

Intervention

Intervention description

The clinical pharmacy intervention took place in the Respiratory Department of a provincial-level general hospital located in southern Vietnam from July to September 2023. This intervention targeted physicians who prescribed antibiotics during the pre-intervention phase. Components of the intervention included pharmacist-led training sessions, individualized consultations for antibiotic dose adjustments based on creatinine clearance (CrCl), and structured drug information sessions emphasizing adherence to guidelines. Physicians with an inappropriate prescribing rate $>30\%$ received three educational sessions, while those below this threshold received one session (details in Suppl. materials 1, 2).

Outcomes and post-intervention evaluation

Primary outcome: the proportion of prescriptions meeting overall appropriateness criteria. Overall appropriateness was defined a priori as meeting all five components—appropriate selection, dose, dosing frequency, duration, and avoidance/management of clinically significant antibiotic-related drug interactions—without differential weighting of components. Secondary outcomes included component-specific appropriateness rates, reasons for regimen change, and an effectiveness index (relative improvement from pre- to post-intervention). Post-intervention evaluation was conducted 3 months after the intervention.

Data analysis

Data completeness and accuracy were verified before analysis. Data were analyzed with SPSS software, version 26.0. Descriptive measures, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Chi-square tests or Fisher's exact tests, as appropriate, were used to compare categorical variables between the pre- and post-intervention periods. Univariate logistic regression was conducted to identify associations between individual factors and inappropriate antibiotic use. Variables with p -values < 0.2 were entered into a multivariate logistic regression model to identify independent predictors of inappropriate prescribing. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Odds ratios (ORs) are reported with 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs).

Ethical considerations

This study was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of Can Tho University of Medicine and Pharmacy (approval number 23.008.HV/PCT-HĐĐĐ, dated 20 March 2023). Because the study used routinely collected hospital medical records and did not involve direct patient interaction or any modification of clinical care, informed consent was not required, per the ethics committee's decision. All patient data were anonymized before analysis, and confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the study.

Study flowchart

A detailed study flowchart illustrating the study design and data collection procedures is presented in Fig. 1.

Results

Characteristics of research subjects

A total of 448 hospitalized AECOPD patient records were reviewed across the two study phases (224 pre-intervention and 224 post-intervention). Patients were predominantly elderly, with mean ages of 67.74 ± 9.48 years

Figure 1. Flowchart of study (screening exclusions were replaced during systematic sampling; therefore, counts of excluded records by reason were not retained). Data table presenting the research findings.

pre-intervention and 70.45 ± 10.45 years post-intervention. More than 90% were male, and the majority had hospital stays exceeding 10 days. Moderate exacerbations accounted for more than 80% of cases in both phases. Additionally, more than 60% of patients had two or more comorbidities, and approximately half exhibited impaired renal function ($\text{CrCl} \leq 50 \text{ mL/min}$). These baseline characteristics did not differ significantly between phases ($p > 0.05$), confirming balanced study cohorts.

The proportion of current smokers declined notably, from 26.8% before the intervention to 17.0% afterward ($p = 0.002$) (Table 1).

Regarding the eight physicians participating in the study, the majority were <40 years old (62.5%), with equal gender distribution (50% male), and most (75%) had undergraduate-level education. Approximately 62.5% had <5 years of clinical experience. Physician characteristics remained consistent across both study phases.

Antibiotic prescription patterns

Among the 224 pre-intervention patient records, 428 antibiotics prescribed within initial regimens were documented. Cephalosporins were the most frequently prescribed antibiotic class (47.9%), predominantly ceftriaxone (17.8%) and cefotaxime (14.0%), followed by aminoglycosides, primarily amikacin (30.8%) (Table 2).

Among antibiotics used in first replacement regimens ($n = 83$ antibiotic entries), the most commonly used antibiotics were piperacillin/tazobactam (19.3%), amikacin (19.3%), and levofloxacin (15.7%). Piperacillin/tazobactam was the most frequently chosen antibiotic in second-line replacements (40%), indicating escalation toward broader-spectrum antibiotics due to clinical deterioration or treatment failure. In third-line replacement regimens ($n = 3$ antibiotic entries), antibiotics targeting multidrug-resistant pathogens—netilmicin, meropenem, and vancomycin—were selected.

Initial antibiotic regimens primarily targeted community-acquired pathogens (89.2%). However, replacement regimens increasingly targeted more resistant organisms such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (30.9% of first replacements, rising to 80% of second replacements) and MRSA (33.3% of third-line replacements), highlighting a clear shift toward broader-spectrum coverage in more complex clinical scenarios.

Treatment regimens and antibiotic appropriateness

In the pre-intervention phase, combination antibiotic therapy was predominant (91.1%), whereas monotherapy was rarely prescribed (8.9%) (Table 3). Most patients (80.8%) did not experience changes in their antibiotic regimens during hospitalization. Among patients requiring

Table 1. Characteristics of study subjects.

Characteristic	Pre-intervention (n, %)	Post-intervention (n, %)	p-value
Age			0.841
≥65 years	149 (66.5%)	152 (67.9%)	
<65 years	75 (33.5%)	72 (32.1%)	
Mean age ± SD	67.74 ± 9.48	70.45 ± 10.45	
Gender			0.492
Male	203 (90.6%)	208 (90.9%)	
Female	21 (9.4%)	16 (7.1%)	
Smoking history			0.002
Current smoker	60 (26.8%)	38 (17%)	
Past smoker	5 (2.2%)	18 (8%)	
No information available	159 (71%)	168 (75%)	
Severity of exacerbation			0.902
Moderate	183 (81.7%)	185 (82.6%)	
Severe	41 (18.3%)	39 (17.4%)	
Comorbidities			0.695
≥2 comorbidities	139 (62.1%)	144 (64.3%)	
<2 comorbidities	85 (37.9%)	80 (35.7%)	
Creatinine clearance (CrCl)			0.508
>50 ml/min	122 (54.5%)	115 (51.3%)	
≤50 ml/min	102 (45.5%)	109 (48.7%)	
Mean CrCl ± SD	53.13 ± 17.23	47.56 ± 15.28	
Hospital stay			0.924
>10 days	131 (58.5%)	130 (58%)	
≤10 days	93 (41.5%)	94 (42%)	
Mean hospital stay ± SD	14.2 ± 8.66	14.22 ± 10.84	

Table 2. Antibiotic use in initial and replacement regimens in the pre-intervention phase.

Group	Antibiotic	Initial (%)	1 st replacement (%)	2 nd replacement (%)	3 rd replacement (%)
Penicillin (3%)	Amoxicillin + Clavulanate	3 (0.7%)	2 (2.4%)	–	–
	Piperacillin + Tazobactam	10 (2.3%)	16 (19.3%)	4 (40%)	–
Cephalosporin (47.9%)	Cefotaxime	60 (14%)	–	–	–
	Cefoperazone	39 (9.1%)	14 (16.9%)	–	–
	Ceftriaxone	76 (17.8%)	–	–	–
	Ceftazidime	30 (7%)	–	–	–
Carbapenem (1.2%)	Imipenem	5 (1.2%)	5 (6%)	–	–
	Meropenem	–	3 (3.6%)	1 (10%)	1 (33.3%)
Quinolone (15.1%)	Ciprofloxacin	1 (0.2%)	6 (7.2%)	3 (30%)	–
	Levofloxacin	41 (9.6%)	13 (15.7%)	–	–
	Moxifloxacin	28 (6.5%)	5 (6%)	–	–
Aminoglycoside (33.1%)	Amikacin	132 (30.8%)	16 (19.3%)	–	–
	Netilmicin	3 (0.7%)	1 (1.2%)	1 (10%)	1 (33.3%)
	Gentamicin	3 (0.7%)	1 (1.2%)	–	–
	Vancomycin	–	1 (1.2%)	1 (10%)	1 (33.3%)
Total		428 (100%)	83 (100%)	10 (100%)	3 (100%)

regimen adjustments, 17% had one change, 1.8% had two changes, and 0.4% required three changes.

The primary reason for antibiotic changes was inadequate clinical improvement (76.7%), followed by results from susceptibility testing (7%) and other miscellaneous clinical considerations (16.3%).

In the pre-intervention phase, antibiotic treatments typically lasted ≤ 10 days (91.5%), with an average du-

ration of 7.84 ± 2.45 days (range: 1–14 days). While appropriateness of antibiotic selection was relatively high (93.3%), appropriateness in dosing (72.8%), frequency of administration (64.3%), and avoidance of clinically significant antibiotic-related drug interactions (64.7%) were notably lower. Overall, only 40.6% of antibiotic prescriptions met comprehensive appropriateness criteria.

Table 3. Treatment regimens and antibiotic appropriateness in the pre-intervention phase.

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Rate (%)
Antibiotic regimens		
Monotherapy	20	8.9%
Combination therapy	204	91.1%
Total regimens	224	100%
Changes in antibiotic therapy		
No change	181	80.8%
One change	38	17%
Two changes	4	1.8%
Three changes	1	0.4%
Total changes	224	100%
Reasons for antibiotic alteration		
Lack of clinical improvement	33	76.7%
Antimicrobial susceptibility testing results	3	7%
Other reasons	7	16.3%
Total alterations	43	100%
Duration of antibiotic therapy		
>10 days	19	8.5%
≤10 days	205	91.5%
Mean duration ± SD	7.84 ± 2.45	–
Minimum duration	1	–
Maximum duration	14	–
Appropriateness of antibiotic use		
Antibiotic selection (rational)	209	93.3%
Dosage (rational)	163	72.8%
Frequency (rational)	144	64.3%
Antibiotic-related interaction avoidance (rational)	145	64.7%
General rationality	91	40.6%

Factors associated with inappropriate antibiotic use

In the pre-intervention phase, inappropriate antibiotic prescribing was significantly more frequent among patients aged ≥ 65 years than among those aged <65 years (70.5% vs. 37.3%; OR = 4.00, $p < 0.001$), among patients with severe exacerbations than among those with moderate exacerbations (82.9% vs. 54.1%; OR = 4.12, $p = 0.001$), among patients with impaired renal function (CrCl ≤ 50 mL/min) than among those with CrCl > 50 mL/min (93.1% vs. 31.1%; OR = 30.00, $p < 0.001$), and among patients receiving combination antibiotic therapy than among those receiving monotherapy (63.7% vs. 15.0%; OR = 9.95, $p < 0.001$). Hospital stay >10 days was also associated with inappropriate prescribing in univariate analysis (OR = 1.73, $p = 0.047$) (Table 4). Prescriber-related characteristics were not significantly linked to inappropriate prescribing practices.

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified severe exacerbation severity (OR = 5.95; $p = 0.001$), impaired renal function (OR = 87.33; $p < 0.001$), and the use of combination antibiotic therapy (OR = 70.93; $p < 0.001$) as independent predictors of inappropriate antibiotic prescribing (Table 4).

Effectiveness of clinical pharmacy intervention

Following the clinical pharmacy intervention, significant improvements were observed across multiple prescribing indicators. Appropriateness in antibiotic selection increased from 93.3% to 97.8% ($p = 0.022$). Appropriateness of dosing improved substantially from 72.8% to 92.9% ($p < 0.001$), frequency of administration improved from 64.3% to 87.9% ($p < 0.001$), and antibiotic-related interaction avoidance rose from 64.7% to 75.4% ($p = 0.013$). Overall prescribing appropriateness significantly improved from 40.6% pre-intervention to 65.6% post-intervention ($p = 0.018$), indicating a marked effectiveness index of 61.6% attributed to the clinical pharmacy intervention (Table 5).

Discussion

Characteristics of research subjects

The demographic profile of the study population was predominantly elderly males aged ≥ 65 years, consistent with prior reports from Vietnam and other Asian countries (Hoang et al. 2023; Vanoverschelde et al. 2023). Although the proportion of current smokers decreased after the intervention (Table 1), smoking cessation counseling was not an explicit component of the intervention; therefore, this change may reflect routine clinical counseling, documentation differences, or secular trends rather than a direct intervention effect. Compared with Ngo (2021), this cohort had more severe exacerbations and longer hospital stays, consistent with the role of the provincial referral hospital in managing more complex AECOPD cases. Physician characteristics, predominantly younger clinicians with limited experience, reflect common staffing constraints in provincial respiratory wards.

Antibiotic prescription patterns

The findings revealed third-generation cephalosporins and aminoglycosides, notably amikacin, as the most frequently prescribed antibiotics, consistent with guidelines from the Vietnamese Ministry of Health, which emphasize broad-spectrum antibiotics due to prevalent local antimicrobial resistance profiles (Vietnam Ministry of Health 2024). These findings corroborate previous national studies, which have similarly highlighted the widespread use of amikacin due to its established efficacy against prevalent local Gram-negative pathogens (Hoang et al. 2023). Moreover, the observed escalation toward broader-spectrum antibiotics, such as piperacillin/tazobactam, ciprofloxacin, and meropenem, during regimen adjustments underscores clinical concerns regarding multidrug-resistant organisms, aligning with observations reported by Nguyen (2022).

In contrast, international guidelines from NICE and GOLD advocate the initial prescribing of narrower-spectrum antibiotics, such as amoxicillin, doxycycline, or

Table 4. Factors associated with inappropriate antibiotic use in the pre-intervention phase.

Associated factors	Rational (%)	Irrational (%)	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Patient-related factors				
Age ≥65 years	44 (29.5)	105 (70.5)	4.00 (2.23–7.19)	<0.001
Age <65 years	47 (62.7)	28 (37.3)	–	–
Hospital stay >10 days	85 (64.9)	61 (35.1)	1.732 (1.007–2.980)	0.047
Hospital stay ≤10 days	48 (51.6)	45 (48.4)	–	–
Moderate exacerbation	84 (45.9)	99 (54.1)	4.12 (1.73–9.77)	0.001
Severe exacerbation	7 (17.1)	34 (82.9)	–	–
<2 comorbidities	37 (43.5)	48 (56.5)	0.489 (0.47–1.42)	0.824
≥2 comorbidities	54 (38.8)	85 (61.2)	–	–
CrCl >50 ml/min	84 (68.9)	38 (31.1)	30.00 (12.72–70.74)	<0.001
CrCl ≤50 ml/min	7 (6.9)	95 (93.1)	–	–
Monotherapy	17 (85)	3 (15)	9.95 (2.82–35.1)	<0.001
Combination therapy	74 (36.3)	130 (63.7)	–	–
Prescriber-related factors				
Prescriber age ≥40 years	20 (37)	34 (63)	0.82 (0.43–1.54)	0.538
Prescriber age <40 years	71 (41.8)	99 (58.2)	–	–
Prescriber gender male	25 (37.9)	41 (62.1)	0.85 (0.47–1.53)	0.589
Prescriber gender female	66 (41.8)	92 (58.2)	–	–
University degree	81 (42.2)	111 (57.8)	0.623 (0.28–1.38)	0.24
Postgraduate degree	10 (31.2)	22 (68.8)	–	–
Clinical experience ≥5 years	13 (33.3)	26 (66.7)	0.686 (0.33–1.41)	0.686
Clinical experience <5 years	78 (42.2)	107 (57.8)	–	–
Multivariate logistic regression analysis:				
Factors				
Age ≥65 years			1.806 (0.81–4.01)	0.148
Hospital stay >10 days			1.564 (0.661–3.699)	0.308
Severe exacerbation			5.95 (2.04–17.29)	0.001
CrCl ≤50 ml/min			87.332 (20–381.29)	<0.001
Combination antibiotic therapy			70.93 (9.37–536.73)	<0.001

Table 5. Rational antibiotic use rates in acute COPD exacerbations.

Characteristic	Pre-intervention (n, %)	Post-intervention (n, %)	Effectiveness index (%)	p-value
Antibiotic selection				
Rational	209 (93.3)	219 (97.8)	4.82%	0.022
Irrational	15 (6.7)	5 (2.2)	–	–
Dosage appropriateness				
Rational	163 (72.8)	208 (92.9)	27.6%	<0.001
Irrational	61 (27.2)	16 (7.1)	–	–
Frequency appropriateness				
Rational	144 (64.3)	197 (87.9)	36.7%	<0.001
Irrational	80 (35.7)	27 (12.1)	–	–
Antibiotic-related interaction avoidance				
Rational	145 (64.7)	169 (75.4)	16.5%	0.013
Irrational	79 (35.3)	55 (24.6)	–	–
Overall rationality				
Rational	91 (40.6)	147 (65.6)	61.6%	0.018
Irrational	133 (59.4)	77 (34.4)	–	–

clarithromycin, unless resistant pathogens are suspected (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2024a; National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2024). Additionally, international literature recommends minimizing aminoglycoside use due to nephrotoxicity risks (Destache 2014). The divergence between Vietnam-

ese and international prescribing practices can be attributed primarily to limited diagnostic capabilities, differences in antimicrobial resistance patterns, and health care resource constraints, underscoring the need for tailored antimicrobial stewardship programs that align with local epidemiological contexts.

Antibiotic regimen duration and appropriateness

Combination antibiotic therapy dominated the prescribing practices in this study, consistent with both national findings at Bach Mai Hospital and international reports involving severe or multidrug-resistant COPD exacerbations (Ma et al. 2021; Bach et al. 2022; Nguyen 2022). The observed mean antibiotic treatment duration (7.84 days) aligns closely with Vietnamese clinical guidelines (Vietnam Ministry of Health 2024) and previous studies by Bach et al. (2022). However, the overall antibiotic appropriateness rate (40.6%) was lower than the 70.25% reported by Ngo (2021). This discrepancy is likely attributable to the more comprehensive assessment used in this study, which incorporates dosing adjustments based on renal function and a structured evaluation of prespecified antibiotic-related drug interactions.

Compared with international studies from high-income settings, which typically report appropriateness rates ranging from 65% to 85% % was lower than the 70.25% reported by Ngo (2021), the lower appropriateness observed in this study highlights critical limitations in diagnostic resources and infrastructure, further stressing the need for more robust antimicrobial stewardship strategies in under-resourced settings.

Risk factors for inappropriate antibiotic therapy

Key patient characteristics linked to inappropriate antibiotic use identified in this study included older age, prolonged hospital stays, severe exacerbations, impaired renal function, and the prescription of combination antibiotic therapy, findings consistent with previous domestic and international research (Dyar et al. 2017; Ngo 2021; Tran et al. 2023). Multivariate regression analysis identified severe exacerbation, impaired renal function, and combination therapy as independent predictors, underscoring the need for targeted clinical pharmacy interventions to address these critical factors. Unlike Dyar et al. (2017), prescriber demographics were not significantly correlated with prescribing appropriateness in this study, aligning more closely with results reported by Pulcini et al. (2015) and Tran et al. (2023).

Impact of clinical pharmacy interventions

The implemented pharmacist-led interventions markedly improved the appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing across multiple dimensions, including antibiotic selection, dosage accuracy, administration frequency, and avoidance of clinically significant antibiotic-related drug interactions. These findings are consistent with previously published Vietnamese studies (Nguyen et al. 2023; Ta et al. 2023; Nguyen et al. 2024; Trinh et al. 2024) and with international literature documenting the efficacy of pharmacist-led stewardship programs (Mekonnen et al.

2016; Skodvin et al. 2021; Gong et al. 2022; Gatechan et al. 2025). Nonetheless, the persistence of relatively high antibiotic-related drug interaction rates post-intervention highlights ongoing challenges in managing complex COPD cases requiring concurrent use of fluoroquinolones and corticosteroids, contrasting with lower interaction rates reported internationally (Skodvin et al. 2021). These findings not only support national stewardship priorities but also provide evidence from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where pharmacist-led interventions remain underutilized despite the high burden of antimicrobial resistance.

Clinical implications: Improvements in antibiotic dose, dosing frequency, and interaction management are clinically meaningful because they are expected to reduce antibiotic-related toxicity (e.g., aminoglycoside nephrotoxicity), prevent avoidable QT prolongation-related arrhythmias, and support earlier clinical stabilization. Although patient-centered outcomes (e.g., acute kidney injury, treatment failure, mortality, and length of stay) were not powered as primary endpoints in this study, future controlled studies should directly quantify how prescribing improvements translate into these outcomes and reduced antimicrobial resistance pressure.

Limitations

The present study has several limitations. First, the before-and-after design did not include a concurrent control group; therefore, improvements may partly reflect secular trends, other quality-improvement activities, or the contemporaneous update of national guidance. Second, the single-center setting and short follow-up limit generalizability and preclude assessment of long-term sustainability. Third, diagnostic constraints, including limited microbiological confirmation, may have led to misclassification of appropriateness for selection and duration. Fourth, the drug–drug interaction assessment was limited to prespecified antibiotic-related combinations and did not comprehensively evaluate interactions among non-antibiotic co-medications. Finally, because the next eligible record replaced excluded records identified during systematic sampling, a complete log of screening failures by reason was not retained; this should be captured in future studies and is acknowledged in the revised flowchart description.

Implications for clinical practice

Despite demonstrating clear effectiveness, the clinical pharmacy interventions did not fully eliminate inappropriate antibiotic prescribing, particularly with renal dosing adjustments and unavoidable antibiotic-related drug interactions. These findings underscore the need for sustained pharmacist involvement through mandatory consultations within multidisciplinary teams and the reinforcement of antimicrobial stewardship programs.

Expanding pharmacist capacity, enhancing training in dosing optimization, and embedding clinical pharmacists into COPD management pathways are critical next steps. Importantly, these results reinforce the global relevance of pharmacist-led interventions, particularly in LMICs where resource constraints heighten the risks of irrational antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Future multicenter research should validate these results and clarify the risk–benefit of frequently co-prescribed antibiotic–corticosteroid regimens, especially fluoroquinolones with corticosteroids in elderly patients.

Conclusion

This study identified substantial gaps in antibiotic prescribing for AECOPD, particularly in dosing optimization and management of antibiotic-related interactions. Pharmacist-led interventions significantly improved appropriateness, reinforcing the essential role of clinical pharmacists in antimicrobial stewardship. These findings extend beyond Vietnam, underscoring the global relevance of pharmacist integration into routine care and policy, particularly in LMICs facing escalating antimicrobial resistance.

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References

- Bach TX, Trung TT, Bui SN, Le TL (2022) A survey of antibiotic usage characteristics in treatment of acute exacerbation of COPD patients in National Hospital 74. *VNU Journal of Science: Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 38(2): 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.25073/2588-1132/vnumps.4408>
- Destache CJ (2014) Aminoglycoside-induced nephrotoxicity – a focus on monitoring: A review of literature. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 27(6): 562–566. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0897190014546102>
- Dyar OJ, Huttner B, Schouten J, Pulcini C, ESGAP (2017) What is antimicrobial stewardship? *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 23(11): 793–798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2017.08.026>
- European Commission CORDIS (2019) The appropriateness of prescribing antibiotics in primary health care in Europe with respect to

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Thang Nguyen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7799-4523>

Huyen My Thi Nguyen <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8241-219X>

Thu Ngoc Chau Phan <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5461-0782>

Data availability

De-identified patient-level data underlying the findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request and with approval from the ethics committee/institution because the dataset contains clinical information derived from hospital medical records.

antibiotic resistance. European Commission, Brussels. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/223083>

- Gatechan T, Nakaranurack C, Plongla R, Chuenjit T, Gross AE (2025) The impact of pharmacist-led education and prospective audit and feedback on antibiotic dose optimization within medical intensive care units in Thailand: A retrospective study. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice* 18(1): 2467456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20523211.2025.2467456>

- Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (2024a) 2024 pocket guide to COPD diagnosis, management, and prevention. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease. https://gold-copd.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/POCKET-GUIDE-GOLD-2024-ver-1.2-11Jan2024_WMV.pdf

- Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (2024b) Global strategy for the prevention, diagnosis and management of COPD: 2024 report. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease, Fontana. <https://goldcopd.org/2024-gold-report/>
- Gong Y, Chen Q, Zhang Y (2022) The role of the clinical pharmacist on the health outcomes of acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (AECOPD). *International Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* 17: 1863–1870. <https://doi.org/10.2147/COPD.S370532>
- Hoang TH, Nguyen KC, Le TL (2023) Characteristics of exacerbation and antibiotic usage in treatment for exacerbation of COPD patients in National Lung Hospital (2022–2023) *VNU Journal of Science: Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 39(4): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.25073/2588-1132/vnumps.4570>
- Luong NLH, Huynh TS, Nguyen NK, Nguyen NH (2022) Evaluation of drug dosage adjustment in patients with renal impairment at Gia Dinh People's Hospital. *Vietnam Medical Journal* 516(2). <https://doi.org/10.51298/vmj.v516i2.3092>
- Ma Y, Huang K, Liang C, Mao X, Zhang Y, Zhan Z, Yang T, Chen Y (2021) Real-world antibiotic use in treating acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (AECOPD) in China: Evidence from the ACURE study. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 12: 649884. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.649884>
- Marins TA, de Jesus GR, Holubar M, Salinas JL, Guglielmi GP, Lin V, de Almeida SM (2024) Evaluation of interventions led by pharmacists in antimicrobial stewardship programs in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic literature review. *Antimicrobial Stewardship & Healthcare Epidemiology* 4: e198. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ash.2024.342>
- Mekonnen AB, McLachlan AJ, Brien JE (2016) Effectiveness of pharmacist-led medication reconciliation programmes on clinical outcomes at hospital transitions: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open* 6: e010003. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-010003>
- Mulchandani R, Tiseo K, Nandi A, Klein E, Gandra S, Laxminarayan R, Van Boeckel TP (2025) Global trends in inappropriate use of antibiotics, 2000–2021: Scoping review and prevalence estimates. *BMJ Public Health* 3: e002411. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjph-2024-002411>
- National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2024) Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (acute exacerbation): Antimicrobial prescribing (NG114). Exceptional surveillance, April 2024. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-96110-8_6019
- Ngo TAL (2021) Investigation of antibiotic use characteristics in the treatment of acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease at the Department of General Medicine, Kien Giang Hospital in 2020. Master's Thesis, Hanoi University of Pharmacy, Hanoi.
- Nguyen LV, Pham LTT, Bui AL, Vi MT, Nguyen NK, Le TT, Pham ST, Nguyen PM, Nguyen TH, Taxis K, Nguyen T, Tran HD (2021) Appropriate antibiotic use and associated factors in Vietnamese outpatients. *Healthcare* 9(6): 693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9060693>
- Nguyen T, Truong MTX, Lam DN, Nguyen HTT, Huynh AM, Duong VK, Vo TPM, Nguyen TH, Cao TTM, Pham ST, Tran BLT, Van Nguyen L (2024) Effectiveness of clinical pharmacist intervention on medication adherence in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: A randomized controlled study. *Patient Education and Counseling* 118: 108037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2023.108037>
- Nguyen TM (2022) Research on improving the effectiveness of antibiotic use in the treatment of acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease at the Respiratory Center, Bach Mai Hospital, through clinical pharmacy activities. PhD Thesis, Hanoi University of Pharmacy, Hanoi.
- Nguyen TNT, Bui QTH, Tran VAT, Tran NQ, Nguyen NTY, Nguyen HT, Pham CTL, Pham HTT, Tran MTP, Dau HTT, Nguyen TTT (2023) Impact of clinical pharmacist-led interventions on switching from intravenous-to-oral antibiotics in patients with infectious diseases at a Vietnamese hospital. *Tropical Medicine & International Health* 28(8): 612–619. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.13911>
- Pulcini C, Wencker F, Frimodt-Møller N, Kern WV, Nathwani D, Rodríguez-Baño J, Simonsen GS, Vlahović-Palčevski V, Gyssens IC, ESGAP Curriculum Working Group (2015) European survey on principles of prudent antibiotic prescribing teaching in undergraduate students. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 21(4): 354–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2014.11.015>
- Sethi S, Murphy TF (2008) Infection in the pathogenesis and course of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 359: 2355–2365. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMr0800353>
- Skodvin B, Høgli JU, Gravningen K, Neteland MI, Harthug S, Akselsen PE (2021) Nationwide audit and feedback on implementation of antibiotic stewardship programmes in Norwegian hospitals. *JAC-Antimicrobial Resistance* 3(2): dlab063. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jacamr/dlab063>
- Ta TDN, Truong AQ, Le MQ, Vu HV, Chau MD, Huynh TN, Nguyen TCT, Nguyen HK, Le BL, Nguyen HH, Dinh TH, Nguyen DT, Nguyen VV, Tran TG, Le TT, Truong TT, Kesteman T, Ashley ED, Anderson DJ, Van Doorn HR, Vu TLH (2023) Review of antibiotic prescriptions as part of antimicrobial stewardship programmes: Results from a pilot implementation at two provincial-level hospitals in Viet Nam. *JAC-Antimicrobial Resistance* 5(1): dlac144. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jacamr/dlac144>
- Tran THN, Pham TS, Nguyen PN, Tran QT (2023) Antibiotic dose adjustment in patients with renal failure at Long An General Hospital in 2022–2023. *Can Tho Journal of Medicine and Pharmacy* 64: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.58490/ctump.2023i64.1259>
- Trinh LP, Le QNT, Le DBT, Vo DQL, Lam DQ, Nguyen TTM, Pham ST, Nguyen T (2024) Effectiveness of pharmacist-led intervention on physicians prescribing for outpatients in Vietnam: A before- and after-intervention study. *Journal of Health Science and Medical Research* 42(4): e20241038. <https://doi.org/10.31584/jhsmr.20241038>
- Vanoverschelde A, Van Hoey C, Buyle F, Den Blauwen N, Depuydt P, Van Braeckel E, Lahousse L (2023) In-hospital antibiotic use for severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease exacerbations: A retrospective observational study. *BMC Pulmonary Medicine* 23: 138. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-023-02426-3>
- Vietnam Ministry of Health (2024) National strategy on antimicrobial resistance prevention and control 2023–2030, vision to 2045. Ministry of Health, Hanoi. <https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/antimicrobial-resistance/amr-spc-npm/nap-library/viet-nam-amr-nap-2024-2025.pdf>
- Vollenweider DJ, Jarrett H, Steurer-Stey CA, Garcia-Aymerich J, Puhan MA (2012) Antibiotics for exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2012(12): CD010257. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD010257>
- Wedzicha JA, Seemungal TAR (2007) COPD exacerbations: Defining their cause and prevention. *The Lancet* 370: 786–796. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(07\)61382-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61382-8)

Supplementary material 1

Drug information leaflet

Authors: Thang Nguyen, Sang Phuoc Hoang, Huyen My Thi Nguyen, Thu Ngoc Chau Phan, Suol Thanh Pham, Phuong Minh Nguyen, Dyah Aryani Perwitasari, Tho Kieu Anh Pham
Data type: pdf

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Supplementary material 2

Hospital-based seminar presentation material

Authors: Thang Nguyen, Sang Phuoc Hoang, Huyen My Thi Nguyen, Thu Ngoc Chau Phan, Suol Thanh Pham, Phuong Minh Nguyen, Dyah Aryani Perwitasari, Tho Kieu Anh Pham
Data type: pdf

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